

INTERLAMINAR STRESSES AT SKIN-STIFFENER INTERFACE

Miguel A. Morell and Manuel Huertas
Construcciones Aeronáuticas S.A.
Engineering Directorate, Stress Office
Avda. John Lennon s/n, Getafe (Madrid) - SPAIN

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a theoretical and experimental investigation carried out to improve the understanding of the nonlinear response of stiffened composite panels with special regard to the disbonding mechanism.

The experimental programme includes the testing of eight flat T stiffened panels under compression and shear loads.

A method of computing the forces in the interface region between the skin and the stiffener has been developed using the MSC/Nastran finite element code. The analytical procedure uses a global nonlinear panel model with a detailed modelization of skin-stiffener interface.

This method becomes in a reliable tool to be used in the structural design of current composite components in aircraft that allows to take advantage of the cost and weight saving potential inherent in the postbuckling capability of these structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The skins of wings and tailplanes are made of panels stiffened by longitudinal stringers. In the case of designs in carbon fibre material, these elements are cocured or cobonded to the skin in the autoclave with pressure and high temperature. When this type of aeronautical construction is working in the postbuckling range, skins deforms out of its plane with the development of loads out of the panel plane. This type of load causes an increase of the interlaminar peeling and shear stresses at skin-stiffener interface. In this condition most typical failure mode is skin-stiffener delamination or debonding.

Currently the derivation of this failure mode requires an extensive and expensive test plan. However the development of analytical tools by using FEM techniques and the last features of the modern computers can reduce and even avoid this testing work.

CASA as lead company in the design and manufacturing of composites structures (HTP A320, HTP A330, HTP A340, EFA wing, MD-11 elevator, B-777 flaps, etc.)

has been working on this subject during the last three years for the generation of a reliable analytical procedure ([1]). This paper presents a theoretical and experimental investigation carried out to improve the understanding of the nonlinear response of stiffened composite panels with special regard to the disbonding mechanism.

2 TEST SPECIMENS

The experimental programme includes the testing of three different flat T stiffened panels under compression and shear loads with a total number of eight panels as it can be seen in table 1. The specimens are a complete section of the skin panel having four stringers chordwise and five ribs spanwise. Skin thickness was chosen to determine the effect of skin postbuckling response on panel performance.

Table 1 : Test matrix

Skin thickness (mm)	Load type	Number of specimens	Strain gauges
5.22	compression	1	48
5.22	shear	1	36
3.06	compression	1	48
3.06	shear	1	36
1.98	compression	2	48
1.98	shear	2	36

Panel dimensions and stacking sequences of skin and stiffeners are both typical of primary structures of Airbus empennages. The panel geometry and stiffener details are shown in Fig 1. Stacking sequences for the skins and stiffeners are given in table 2.

Fig. 1 : Specimen geometry

The material used for panel production was AS4/8552 tape with the following typical properties : $E_1 = 120000$ MPa, $E_2 = 9000$ MPa, $G_{12} = 3700$ MPa, $\nu_1 = 0.3$, $t = .18$ mm. Energy levels corresponding to barely visible damages were determined for each panel thickness and position on a witness panel. All specimens include artificial and low velocity barely visible damages at critical locations in order to simulate in service conditions.

Table 2 : Skin and stiffener laminates.

skin thickness 5.22 mm	(45/ - 45/0/ - 45/45/90/ - 45/45/45/ - 45/0/ - 45/45/90/0)S
skin thickness 3.06 mm	(45/ - 45/0/ - 45/45/90/ - 45/45/0)S
skin thickness 1.98 mm	(45/ - 45/0/ - 45/45/90/45/ - 45/0/ - 45/45)
longitudinal stiffener web	(45/ - 45/0 ₃ /90/0 ₃ / - 45/45)S
transverse stiffener web	(45/ - 45/ - 45/45/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/45/ - 45/ - 45/45)S

3 TEST RESULTS

The shear load was introduced through a shear frame composed of four high stiffness beams. Specimens were jointed by two rows of bolts to the frame which was loaded in tension in one diagonal direction. The compression load was introduced through a compression frame composed of two pairs of high stiffness beams in the unloaded edges and two rigid yokes through which specimen was loaded. All testing were carried out at RT/AR conditions.

During the testing, strains measured in different points of the structure was recorded. Table 3 summarizes the principal items of test results. Values shown are average measurements among different strain gauges at equivalent locations of skin. As expected, postbuckling capacity increases with the panel width/thickness ratio, being the increment greater for shear loaded panels.

Table 3 : Test results

Panel code	Skin thickness (mm)	Load type	Buckling microstrain ($\mu\epsilon$)	Buckling load (kN)	Failure load (kN)	Postbuckling capability
1	5.22	compre.	-4470	1500	1544	3%
2	3.06	compre.	-3000	677	902	33%
3	5.22	shear	-	-	2180	0%
4	3.06	shear	5616	935	1043	11%
5	1.98	compre.	-1956	-380	-659	73%
6	1.98	compre.	-1700	-300	-612	104%
7	1.98	shear	2500	290	548	89%
8	1.98	shear	2670	300	578	93%

The difference between the initial buckling load of specimens number 5 and 6 was explained due to bowing of the specimen number 5 which produced an increase of the panel local buckling load.

Failure was explosive for both types of load. For compression, the mode of failure was a skin-stringer delamination that led to the collapse of specimen. The skin-stringer separation occurred for full stringer length and in some regions the stiffener flange came away from the panel with part of the first 45° skin ply. For shear panels, the mode of failure was a separation from skin of lateral stringers at corners with transverse stiffener.

4 ANALYSIS

A method of computing the forces in the interface region between the skin and the stiffener has been developed using the MSC/Nastran finite element code ([2], [3]). This method can be implemented on finite element models where skin and stringers are modelled using four nodes quadrilateral plate elements (QUAD4 elements in MSC/Nastran) considering the skin-stiffener interface as a resin layer with thickness estimated around 16µm for the AS4/8552 material. At the skin-stiffener interface, a group of nodes are created in the skin upper surface and another similar group in the stringer flange lower surface (Fig. 2). The distance between both nodes groups is the interface thickness. The first group is joined through rigid elements (RBAR elements in MSC/Nastran) to skin nodes while the second group is joined to the stringer flange nodes (also through RBAR elements). This modelization allows to know the displacements at the bottom of stiffener flange and at the top of the skin. The interface layer is modelled with beam elements (BEAM elements in MSC/Nastran) which connect both groups of nodes. Axial and shear beam stiffness are taken to reproduce the interface layer stiffness while the bending and torsional beam stiffness are negligible. The beam element cross section area is the area associated for each node (border beam elements will have the cross area half of interior beam element cross area).

The analytical procedure uses a global nonlinear panel model and conjugates the influence of the global postbuckling deformation and the effects of local three-dimensional stresses at skin-stiffener interface allowing to sort out critical regions along the stiffener, where the starting point of the delamination is situated.

Fig. 2 : Skin-stiffener interface idealization.

The Fig. 3 shows a scaled deformed view of the panel finite element model. The agreement between model and testing was demonstrated in the pre and postbuckling regime as it is shown in the Fig. 4 for the 3.06 mm thick compression panels where a comparison between the longitudinal skin strains at the center point of a bay in the model and in the testing is made. Good correlation was achieved between the test results and theoretical predictions.

Fig. 3 : Global view of finite element model.

Fig. 4 : Longitudinal skin strains comparison.

Distributions of interlaminar stresses along the skin-stiffener interface at different bondlines and at different load levels were determined. Fig. 5 shows typical stress distribution within this region. Below local buckling load interlaminar normal stresses (σ_z) are negligible and the distributions of interlaminar shear stresses (τ_{zx} and τ_{yz})

are regular. Above local buckling load the normal stresses increase their values and the shear stresses distributions become irregular.

Fig. 5 : Interlaminar stresses distributions along the stiffener.

The distributions of interlaminar stresses depend on the relative displacements between skin and stiffeners. The τ_{zx} distribution is directly affected by relative displacements normal to the stiffener axis and τ_{yz} by relative displacements along the stiffeners. The peeling stresses σ_z are produced by differences in bending stiffness between the stringers and the skin normal to the axis of the stringer and its distribution is affected by relative displacements normal to the skin. The initial disbonding is caused by an interaction between peeling and shear stresses in these locations. The failure criterion could be formulated as follows :

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_{z.all}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{zx}}{\tau_{zx.all}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{yz}}{\tau_{yz.all}}\right)^2 \leq 1$$

It has to be noted that for the component σ_z only positive values (normal tension that produces the peeling) will be taken into account in the failure criterium. Negative values of σ_z mean forces that prevent the peeling.

To applied this failure criterium it is necessary to assume a values of the allowables stresses. The values of these allowables are found experimentally.

The point corresponding to the theoretical maximum interlaminar stresses coincide with the localization of failure initiation of the test panels.

5 CONCLUSIONS

An analytical procedure has been developed to predict interlaminar stresses at skin-stiffener interface. This method becomes in a reliable tool to be used in the structural design of current composite components in aircraft that allows to take advantage of the cost and weight saving potential inherent in the postbuckling capability of these structures. The application of this technology to the A340 tails might lead to a skin weight saving of around 2.5%.

6 REFERENCES

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